

Dependently Generative Empty Stages Theory of Ontology of Dance-Work

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Abstract

This essay presents Dependently Generative Empty Stages (DGES) theory to explain the ontology of dance work as an artifact. This essay critiques the views within analytical ontology art works that treat repeatable works such as music and dance as fixed "types" or "space-time worms". Because these views maintain the art work integrity over time. This work argues that the bodily and fluid nature of dance art invalidates these continuity-based approaches. The essay primarily argues that the conservative views of Nicholas Wolterstorff, who defines artwork as a norm-based fixed type (Norm-Kind), and Nurbay Irmak, who defines it as a created abstract artifact, don't meet to explain the concrete and variable reality of dance. The essay also argues that the "Perdurantism" model proposed by Ben Caplan and Carl Matheson imposes an artificial ontological unity on radically different performances when applied to dance. In this

context, the essay proposes a new model that synthesizes Theodore Sider's metaphysical "Stage Theory" (Exdurantism) with the Buddhist principle of "Dependent Co-Arising" (Pratītyasamutpāda). According to this model, the dance work is a decentralized, scattered cluster of generative stages. Each performance is ontologically autonomous but emerges causally dependent on the previous stage. Therefore, different performances are not parts of the "same" work. As David Lewis describes, different performances separated only by a "Counterpart Relation" and their identities are established through the viewer's gaze and convention.

Keywords: *ontology of dance, stage theory, exdurantism, perdurantism, space-time, somatic, generative, dependent co-arising, Pratītyasamutpāda, dependent empty stage*

Dependently Generative Empty Stages Theory of Ontology of Dance-Work

Understanding the ontology of the dance-work is a confrontation with the fluid, discontinuous, and somatic reality of the performing body. The embodied reality of the dance is in a constant state of flux; this nature makes a rigid identity impossible. Because of that I reject Nicholas Wolterstorff's Norm-Kinds and Nurbay Irmak's Abstract Artifacts views. Since dance, including choreographed classical works, is not an abstract idea but a concrete, bodily, and temporal event. In

the second section of the paper, I will explain and criticize Wolterstorff's and Irmak's theories. Wolterstorff defines works of art as Norm-Kinds that have conditions of correctness. According to him, for a performance to be considered a work of art, it must conform to predetermined criteria. This view treats the human body, which is the instrument of dance, as a stable object. However, since the body is constantly changing in dance (aging, injury, etc.), it is impossible to maintain a standard norm.

After moving beyond theories that could be considered conservative in the second section, in the third section I will address the perdurantism theory presented by Ben Caplan and Carl Matheson. In this section, I will explain and criticize the view that a work of art is a space-time worm which is a whole unfolding in time. However, I also find this view insufficient for explaining a work of art, as it speaks of a whole that has a beginning and emerges from its parts.

Instead of the views I discussed in previous sections, in the fourth section I will explain Theodore Sider's Exdurantism model. This view posits that each performance is ontologically a separate and autonomous stage. The connection between these stages is not identity, but merely a counterpart relationship. I also adopted this view while formulating my own thesis. I am expanding on Sider's Stage Theory model with the Buddhist principle of dependent co-arising.

Lastly, in the conclusion section I will emphasize my thesis. It is futile to seek a fixed essence in

dance. Analytical ontologies (Wolterstorff, Irmak, Caplan & Matheson) attempt to salvage the work as a fixed substance or an integrated worm. However, this denies the impermanence of dance as artwork. I expand upon Sider's exdurantism theory with the Buddhist aspect of co-arising. The dance work is a decentralized, scattered cluster of generative stages. These stages are ontologically separate but emerge causally in a dependent manner.

I. The Necessity of Leaving Conservative Ontology Behind

The aim of this chapter is to examine the attempt of analytic ontology to attribute a fixed "essence" to the work and to show why this attempt falls short in the face of the somatic reality of dance work. To this end, I consider the views of Wolterstorff and Irmak.

I.I.I. Wolterstorff: Art-Work as Norm-Kind

The concept of 'Kinds' lies at the heart of Wolterstorff's ontology. According to him, works of art are universal genres with specific conditions of conformity. He classifies artworks like drama as Performance-works. He says, "*Performance-works and object-works are kinds (types, sorts)—kinds whose examples are the performances or objects of those works*". (Wolterstorff, 1975, p. 126)

Furthermore, the most defining characteristic of these works is their "Norm-Kind" nature; that is, for a performance to be considered a work of art, it must meet a specific set of "Correctness Conditions": "*For any predicate P which is*

acceptable with respect to W... if there is some property being P... such that it is impossible that something should be a correctly formed example of W and lack being P, then P is true off" (Wolterstorff, 1975, p. 125) The crucial point is that Wolterstorff conceives of the work as a Platonic 'Genre'. The work exists as a set of rules before and independently of its performances. Performances, in turn, are the reflections of these rules (norms) in the physical world. Therefore, for Wolterstorff, the identity of a work lies in its conformity to these norms. For a sequence of sounds or a movement to belong to that work, it must be correct, he says: "For a production of a sound-sequence to be an occurrence of a work W, it must be an occurrence of the sound-sequence of W which is correct".

Adapting Wolterstorff's approach to dance, a dance work, such as *The Dying Swan* Ballet is a movement sequence determined by the choreographer. The dancer's task is to "correctly" instantiate this abstract norm in the physical world.

I.I.II. Anti-Essentialist Criticism

Wolterstorff establishes the work with correctness conditions, which is the unchanging essence of the work. However, in dance, the body, as the instrument of artistic performance, is in constant flux and change. Wolterstorff considers the dancer's body like a piano, seemingly standard and unchanging. Yet every body is different at every moment; the same dancer will perform the same choreography differently when young, injured, or old. What Wolterstorff calls "norm" is an imaginary

standard in the face of somatic reality. The movements of an aging body, for example, that of the famous dancer Maya Plisetskaya, may not conform to the "seemingly norms" of choreography, but this is the somatic evolution of the work.

Wolterstorff's theory codes bodily changes, like aging as a "deviation." I, however, argue that this change is the very nature of the work's existence. In my view, Maya Plisetskaya's 60-year-old *The Dying Swan* performance is not a "deficient" instance of the performance-work. Rather, I argue it's a completely new and autonomous stage. Wolterstorff's concept of "kind" remains like an artificial cage that attempts to freeze the fluidity of the body.

Wolterstorff, by viewing the work as an eternal "Genre", misses the historical and human dimension of dance. From his perspective, *The Dying Swan* existed as a possibility even before the choreographer Michel Fokine was born; Fokine merely 'discovered' it. This also fails to explain the somatic creativity of dance.

I.II.I. Irmak: Art-Work as a Created Abstract Artifact

Nurbay Irmak advocates for creationism and opposes Wolterstorff's Platonic implication that art-works are eternal entities. According to Irmak, works are created by humans. However, Irmak argues that this created thing is still an abstract artifact. Abstract artifacts are created, but once created, they are abstract objects that lack spatial

location (Irmak, 2020). Irmak takes a step further by historicizing the work. According to him, the work is a created entity ontologically dependent on the intention of its creator. However, for him, this entity is still an abstract object, detached from space-time.

Applying Irmak's view on dance, a dance work is an object created in the choreographer's mind and intention, becoming visible in the physical world as performance. The work comes into existence the moment the composer/choreographer creates it; yet, it still remains essentially abstract.

I.II.II. Criticism of Abstract Artifacts

While Irmak's theory addresses the problem of creation, namely genesis of the work, it falls short in the face of dance's nature of inherent concreteness and persistence.

Irmak claims that the work "lacks spatial location" (Irmak, 2020). However, dance is inherently a spatial and concrete art, embodied in the dancer's body. An abstract dance work cannot exist, independent of a dancer who sweats, resists gravity, and occupies space on stage. To define the work as an abstract artifact is to attribute to it a "ghostly self" essence, independent of the body, even if not Platonic.

Furthermore, Irmak assumes that the work is completed at the moment of its creation. However, in the "stage theory" and "dependent co-arising" model that I advocate, as I will explain later, the work is never truly complete. The work is

ontologically dependent not only on its creator and the state in which it was created in the past, but also on the performer at that moment, on the present. The work is not an abstract object, as Irmak claims, but rather the concrete stages of performance itself. There is not any independent graspable essence of the art-work as it is.

Dance, by its very nature, is a concrete art. It consists of flesh, bone, sweat, and gravity. There is no abstract existence of the Dying Swan outside the space occupied by the dancer on stage. Irmak's definition of "abstract artifact" does not encompass the bodily materialism of dance. I argue that the dance-work is not an "idea," but an "event." When it comes to dance, Irmak's theory explains the "moment of birth" of the work, but it cannot explain its "life." Dance works must be "reborn" in every performance, even after the choreographer dies. The work is ontologically dependent not only on its creator but also on the dancer at that moment. Irmak's theory freezes the work as a completed object after it is created; whereas I argue that the work is an unfinished process that is recreated in each phase.

II. The Limits of the Standard Perdurantism

In the second section, I argued that dance cannot be an abstract artifact due to its embodied nature and raised the problem of concreteness. In analytical philosophy, one of the strongest alternatives that views the art-work as a concrete object is Ben Caplan and Carl Matheson's "musical

perdurantism" theory. This theory sees the work as a physical whole that extends over time. Caplan and Matheson's perdurantism (worm theory) view seems, at first glance, a perfect solution for dance because it sees the work as a concrete and temporal entity. While this theory solves the concreteness problem I mentioned in the second section of the paper, it raises a new error by attempting to unify the fragmented structure of dance. There is no such thing as the essence of the work, in other words, work itself. There are only a series of instantaneous events in the dance.

II.I Worm Theory

Caplan and Matheson view the musical work as a Space-Time Worm composed of a collection of performances. The work perdures through time: "*According to Perdurantism about Musical Works, musical works persist by perduring: that is, by having different temporal parts at every time at which they exist*" (Caplan & Matheson, 2006, p. 60). According to this view, performances are not instances of the work; rather, they are parts of the work.

Caplan and Matheson reject "type" theories. Because abstract types, like numbers or triangles, cannot be created; they have existed from eternity. To preserve our intuition that musical-works are created and concrete, they argue that they are "Four-Dimensional Objects". According to them, a musical work is a "Space-Time Worm" that extends through time, stretching from the past to the future.

That is, a work consists of the fusion of all its performances.

Applying this to dance, to explain the "created" and embodied physical nature of dance, they define the work as a concrete whole with parts in time. For example, *The Dying Swan* ballet is not an abstract choreography, but a colossal, flesh-and-blood somatic worm composed of all *The Dying Swan* performances from 1877 to the present day. Anna Pavlova's performance is a temporal segment of this worm from 1905. The work is a tangible historical entity that grows over time as new performances are added.

II.II Criticism: Dance is Discontinuous

Caplan and Matheson posit that all the different performances merge to form a single work. Perdurantism takes a correct step by concretizing the work, but it attributes a unity to dance by the "worm" metaphor that implies an organic continuity and structural unity between the parts.

There is no structural connection strong enough to make the performances of different bodies parts of a single object in dance. The ontological chasm between Pavlova's performance and a modern avant-garde interpretation of the choreography is too vast to regard them as parts of the same "worm." It is to impose a forced identity on disconnected events. Caplan and Matheson's "worm" remains too unified for the chaotic nature of dance work. Dance performances are radically different and there are heaps of disconnected

moments, discontinuous events lacking a structural center. Performances occurring simultaneously in different parts of the world, in different bodies, form a decentralized "Scattered Cluster." There is no single worm; there is a network of events spread across space-time.

III. Dance as Stages: Exdurantism in Dance-Work

In the third section, I rejected the worm theory, which describes a whole composed of parts, because this theory does not fit the nature of dance, which is devoid of essence. And I now argue that the only model that explains the nature of dance is exdurantism. By adding the Buddhist metaphysics and the perspective of selflessness and intrinsic absence to this theory, I propose a new thesis on the ontology of dance.

III.I. Sider's Exdurantism

Theodore Sider argues that objects are instantaneous stages. According to him, the past self or the future self is not "a part of me," but merely other objects related to me. According to Sider's theory of exdurantism or Stage view, objects are not enduring entities. Sider identifies the object with the instantaneous "stage" itself. He says:

The Newtonian theory of enduring places is known as a theory of 'absolute position' because the notion of remaining in one and the same place over time is well-defined on the theory—it is simply continuing to be located at one and the same enduring place. The problem is that there is no

empirical basis for assuming that absolute comparisons of position make any sense. (Sider, 2001, p.28)

There is no such thing as a vast, ever-extending entity called "The Dance-Work." There is only the performance taking place on stage at that moment. Because of that, Pavlova's dance is not a part of the dance-work called *"The Dying Swan"*. The performance is an entity in its own right. The same is true of Plisetskaya's or any other artist's dance. Therefore, Pavlova and Plisetskaya's performances are not parts of the same work, but independent entities in a "counterpart relation" with each other.

According to Sider, objects do not extend through time, they only exist as instantaneous Stages. So, "I" am not the sum of past and future parts; I am only the "present" stage. Given the radical variability of dance, Sider's "Stage Theory" (Exdurantism) offers a more suitable ontological foundation. According to Sider, persistence in time is not about an object extending through time, but about instantaneous phases and their counterparts: According to the stage view, persisting objects do not endure through time, nor do they perish by having temporal parts. Rather, they exist at an instant (Sider, 2001).

III.II Looking through the lens of Buddhism: Conventional Truth

In this section, I will ground the metaphysical foundation of Sider's stage theory in the Buddhist philosophy's two truths doctrine and Nagarjuna's concept of emptiness (Śūnyatā). My aim is to

reconstruct the ontological status of the dance work through the concept of no-self.

As Mark Siderits details, the Buddhist philosopher Nagasena, in his dialogue with King Milinda, proposes two different levels of truth for understanding existence: "Conventional Truth" and "Ultimate Truth" (Siderits, 2007). The ultimate truth is that only momentary fragments (dharma/skandhas) are real. Wholes, such as the self, the forest, or the car, do not actually exist. Beings lack an essence that would make them whole and permanent. Everything is in a state of flux and transience. Conventional truth is that, for practical reasons, we give names to masses of momentary fragments; for example, we call the sum of the parts "the car." This is a construct that does not reflect reality, but it is a convenient designator.

...The conventional truth is that I am a person who has existed for some time. I experience this existence as involving there being a 'me' who is aware of the different experiences that this 'I' has. Right now I am aware of reading these words and thinking about these ideas. Earlier this same 'I' was aware of other experiences... (Siderits, 2007, p.63)

Applying this perspective to dance, like the car, *The Dying Swan* does not exist at the level of ultimate truth. It only exists in stages. The dance-work is merely a conventional label we give to this heap of stages.

However, the analysis doesn't end here. Nagasena's view that "there is no car, only parts" can still cause

a dualist understanding (existence/non-existence duality). Therefore, Nagarjuna argues that the two truths are not mutually exclusive with his "Middle Way" view. He points out that dependent co-arising and emptiness are the same thing. In the *Mūlamadhyamakakārikā*, Nagarjuna points to the identity of emptiness:

Whatever is dependently co-arisen /
That is explained to be emptiness. / That,
being a dependent designation, / Is itself the
middle way (Nagarjuna, 1995, Chapter 24,
Verse 18)

According to Nagarjuna, something being "empty" does not mean it does not exist; it means it lacks intrinsic nature (Svabhāva - independent essence). If a dance piece had a fixed essence, it could never be performed and could never exist again in another body, as it could never change. The dance-work can exist precisely because it is "empty of essence," and for this reason, it is destined to change in each performance. The dance work is "selfless." This selflessness is the dynamic potential of the work. Since *The Dying Swan* lacks a fixed essence, Pavlova can perform it as Pavlova in Pavlova's body, and Plisetskaya in Plisetskaya's body. Emptiness is the ground that allows the stages to emerge.

IV. Dependent Empty Stages: The Emptiness of the Dance-Work

Ultimately, when we combine stated Buddhist views with Stage Theory, the dance work ontologically consists only of momentary,

essenceless and interdependent, empty stages. Phenomenologically, the viewer, by calling this series of empty stages "dance-work", gives it a temporary identity as dependent designation. Thus by accepting its emptiness, an ontological space is opened up for the dance's endless flux.

IV.I The Mechanism: Generative Stages & Dependent Co-Arising

Sider's Stage theory establishes a logical and static relationship by pointing to the existence of different stages and their interrelationships. In my thesis, this structure becomes dynamic and productive with the addition of dependent co-arising from Buddhism.

Stages are productive and generative forces. One stage of a dance movement physically and intentionally gives rise to the next stage of movement. And each performer enriches the dance as they perform, adding something from their own world. In this context, Pavlova's performance and Plisetskaya's performance cannot be the same since they both generated their own version. However, Plisetskaya's performance "emerges dependently" from the historical and bodily chain initiated by Pavlova. The connection between them is not one of sameness, but rather a causal lineage.

The identity of the dance-work is an institutional counterparthood. It is not metaphysics but the audience that grants a temporary identity to a series of empty phases through dependent designation.

IV.II. Solving the Problem of Sameness: Subjective Similarity

With the Dependently Generative Empty Stages thesis I propose in this essay, each performance is freed from the burden of being an instance, a copy or a (temporal) part. Each performance is a complete, autonomous object proper in its own right.

In dance, the instruments of the art-work, bodies are so different that the similarity is entirely a subjective and contextual similarity left to the viewer's interpretation. It is the subjective bridge of the community that establishes the institutional counterparthood between different works. Audience, choreographer, performer... According to this view, all witnesses are components that decide what the performance is. This is not a metaphysical necessity but a conventional co-arising.

Conclusion

To view dance as an "created abstract artifact" or an "integrated worm" is to deny the chaos of the environment and the body. The most suitable model for the ontology of dance is Stage Theory since the dance-work is neither eternal nor abstract; it is a concrete, instantaneous, and constantly recreated "stage". There is no such thing as a "single" dance-work. However, in dance performance, there are only momentarily appearing and constantly changing bodily states. There are an infinite number of separated, unique and instantaneous artistic stages.

As I discussed in the beginning of the essay, the dance work is neither a fixed "genre" as Wolterstorff called it, nor a unified "worm" as Caplan & Matheson called it. In contrast, according to the principle of Pratīyasamutpāda, nothing, including abstract objects, can remain independent and static, unaffected by circumstances. The dance work is dependent generative stages that give rise to each other through the laws of dependent co-mergence, as understood in Sider's Stage Theory and Nagarjuna's Buddhist ontology, and are conventionally combined in the mind of the viewer. The work is empty of inherent existence, and it is precisely this emptiness that allows it to be reborn with infinite variations in each performance.

References

- Albahari, M. (2006). *Analytical Buddhism: The two-tiered illusion of self*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Caplan, B., & Matheson, C. (2006). Defending musical perdurantism. *British Journal of Aesthetics*, 46(1), 59–69.
- Casati, R., & Varzi, A. C. (1999). *Parts and places: The structures of spatial representation*. The MIT Press.
- Conroy, R., & Bresnahan, A. (2025). The philosophy of dance. In E. N. Zalta & U. Nodelman (Eds.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Fall 2025 ed.). <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2025/entries/dance/>
- Davies, D. (2004). *Art as performance*. Blackwell.
- Garfield, J. L. (1995). *The fundamental wisdom of the middle way: Nagarjuna's Mulamadhyamakakarika*. Oxford University Press.
- Irmak, N. (2020). The problem of creation and abstract artifacts. *Synthese*, 197, 3963–3978.
- Lewis, D. (1986). *On the plurality of worlds*. Blackwell.
- McFee, G. (2011). *The philosophical aesthetics of dance*. Dance Books.
- Sider, T. (2001). *Four-dimensionalism: An ontology of persistence and time*. Oxford University Press.
- Siderits, M. (2007). *Buddhism as philosophy: An introduction*. Ashgate.
- Wolterstorff, N. (1975). Toward an ontology of art works. *Noûs*, 9(2), 115–142.